

Effects of Fiber Type and Cooling Rate on the Crystallization Behaviour of Low-Melt PAEK Thermoplastic Composites

K.Gordnian¹, A.Forghani¹, D.Howell², A.McKee¹, M.Roy¹, T.Ytre-Eide³, G.Fernlund¹, A.Chadwick⁴, T.Wiedmann⁴, H.Voggenreiter⁴, and A. Poursartip^{1,3}

¹Convergent Manufacturing Technologies, Vancouver, BC, Canada

²Toray Advanced Composites, Morgan Hill, CA, USA

³Composites Research Network, Department of Materials Engineering, The University of British Columbia, Vancouver, BC, Canada

⁴German Aerospace Centre (DLR), Stuttgart, Germany

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Physics-Based Process Simulation

- Physics-based modelling is founded on our understanding of causality of events
- The phenomena of interest are modelled using mathematical representations
- In Process Simulation, a physics-based model needs to include representations of:
 - **Material**
 - **Shape**
 - **Tooling**
 - **Equipment**
 - **Process**
- The more complex the system, the more useful process simulation becomes!
- Process simulation should be used at all stages of the lifecycle of a product, even before building the equipment and tooling

Source: <https://compositeskn.org/KPC/A208>

Process Simulation Workflow

Different Analysis Types and Outcomes

Importance of Crystallization/Melt Kinetics

- Degree of crystallinity: Key state variable for all downstream material models in thermoplastic composites process simulation.
- Thermoplastic composites continuously undergo crystallization and melting during manufacturing processes.
- Cooling rate significantly impacts the degree of crystallinity in the final composite part.
- Unlike thermoset cure kinetics, thermoplastic crystallization kinetics can be influenced by the fiber type.

Importance of Crystallization/Melt Kinetics

- Toray Cetex® TC1225 LM-PAEK composites:
 - Lower processing temperatures due to reduced melt temperature.
 - High service temperatures comparable to PEEK and PEKK due to similar glass transition temperatures.
- TC1225 UD tapes available with various fibers, notably T700G and T1100G.
- Study objectives:
 - Investigate cooling rate and fiber type (T700G, T1100G) effects on crystallization behaviour.
 - Develop crystallization/melt kinetics models for accurate process simulations.

Materials and Methodology

- Case Study Materials:
 - Toray Cetex[®] TC1225 LM-PAEK UD tape, two fibre types:
 - T1100G
 - T700G
 - $T_g = 147\text{ °C}$ (297 °F)
 - $T_m^0 = 305\text{ °C}$ (581 °F)
 - Processing temperature: 340 – 385 °C (644 – 725 °F)
 - Resin mass fraction: 34%
- Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) tests (Using a PerkinElmer DSC 8500 machine):
 - Dynamic melt crystallization tests (1 CPM – 250 CPM)
 - Isothermal melt crystallization tests
 - Dynamic melting tests (1 CPM – 250 CPM)

Experimental Results: TC1100G-Effect of Cooling Rate

Dynamic Melt Crystallization

Cooling at 1 °C/min

Cooling at 10 °C/min

Experimental Results: TC1100G-Effect of Cooling Rate

Dynamic Melt Crystallization

Cooling at 20 °C/min

Cooling at 90 °C/min

Effect of Cooling Rate on Crystallization

- Experimental Observations:
 - Increasing the cooling rate shifts crystallization initiation to lower temperatures.
 - Completion of crystallization also occurs at lower temperatures as cooling rate increases.
- Impact on Degree of Crystallinity:
 - Higher cooling rates lead to a decrease in the final degree of crystallinity.
 - Reduced crystallinity can influence mechanical and thermal performance of the composite.

Experimental Results: TC1100G

Isothermal Melt Crystallization

Isothermal at 290 °C

Isothermal at 265 °C

Experimental Results: TC1100G

Dynamic Melting

Heating at 10 °C/min

Heating at 60 °C/min

Experimental Results: Effect of Fibre Type

Low Cooling Rate (5°C/min)

Experimental Results: Effect of Fibre Type

Low Cooling Rate (90°C/min)

Experimental Results: Effect of Fibre Type

Temperature at Maximum Crystallization Rate:

Crystallization-Melt Kinetics

- Most of the works in the literature consider isothermal or non-isothermal crystallization, separately, while in reality, cycles are combined
- Most crystallization kinetics models in the literature do not account for the induction time
- There are very few works which consider melt kinetics models
- We believe that state-of-the-art crystallization/melt kinetics models for thermoplastics must include:
 - Rate type (differential form): suitable for an arbitrary temperature cycle
 - Induction time
 - Accurate representation of melt kinetics

Crystallization Kinetics

Iso-conversional Crystallization Data – T1100G Fibre

$X = 0.02$

$X = 0.15$

Crystallization Kinetics Model

- No significant difference in crystallization mechanisms in isothermal and non-isothermal crystallization.

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = K(T)f(X)$$

- Two competing mechanisms in crystallization:

$$(T_m^0 - T) \nearrow \Rightarrow \frac{dX}{dt} \nearrow \quad \quad \quad (T - T_g) \searrow \Rightarrow \frac{dX}{dt} \searrow$$

$$K(T) = K_0 e^{\frac{-E_g}{R(T-T_g)}} e^{\frac{-E_m}{R(T_m^0 - T)}}$$

- There is an “induction time” model to capture the induction time or incubation period.

Crystallization Kinetics-Predictions- T1100G Fibre

Dynamic Melt Crystallization

Cooling at 1 °C/min

Cooling at 10 °C/min

Crystallization Kinetics-Predictions- T1100G Fibre

Dynamic Melt Crystallization

Cooling at 20 °C/min

Cooling at 90 °C/min

Melt Kinetics Model

- Master melt curve and crystallization kinetics model used for prediction of crystallinity during melting and crystallization
- Crystallization/Recrystallization Increment

$$\Delta X_c = \begin{cases} \frac{dX_c}{dt} \Delta t & X < X_{max} \\ 0 & X = X_{max} \end{cases}$$

- Melting Increment

$$\Delta X_m = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{dX}{dT} \right)_{\text{master}} \Delta T & \dot{T} > 0 \\ 0 & \dot{T} \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

- Updating X

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta X &= \Delta X_c + \Delta X_m \\ X^n &= X^{n-1} + \Delta X \end{aligned}$$

(Gordnian, 2017)

Melt Kinetics-Predictions- T1100G Fibre

Dynamic Melting

Heating at 10 °C/min

Heating at 60 °C/min

Model Predictions-Effect of Cooling/Heating Rate- T1100G Fibre

Crystallization

Melting

Model: Effect of Fibre Type

Can one material model predict the crystallization kinetics of CF/LM-PAEK for another fiber type?

Summary and Conclusions

- Toray Cetex® TC1225 LM-PAEK/T1100G UD tape and Toray Cetex® TC1225 LM-PAEK/T700G UD tape were characterized for crystallization and melt kinetics
- Increasing the cooling rate shifts crystallization initiation to lower temperatures.
- Higher cooling rates lead to a decrease in the final degree of crystallinity.
- Fiber type affects both the induction time and the crystallization behavior. A complete crystallization kinetics characterization is required for each fiber type.

References

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Thank You!